

FORUM

Connections in computational proteomics 2024

Acknowledgement of Country

In recognition of the deep history and culture of this continent, I wish to acknowledge the traditional owners and custodians of the land upon which we meet; and pay respect to elders past and present.

Kurna people (Adelaide)

Wurundjeri Woi-wurrung and Bunurong peoples (Melbourne)

Housekeeping

In an emergency

Toilets

Any and all questions can be added to our event [shared document online](#)

Photos

Afternoon tea
Morning tea

Dinner tonight
(at own expense)

Welcome!

Forum agenda

Tuesday 30th

- 1:00 pm Welcome and introductions
- 1:20 pm Invited speaker presentations & ask me anything
- 2:35 pm Afternoon tea and networking
- 3:00 pm Strategic discussion: Addressing the key challenges in computational proteomics
- 4:00 pm Interactive session: Preview of a shared platform for computational proteomics (Proteomics Lab)
- 5:00 pm Wrapping up day 1
- 6:00 pm Dinner - at own expense

Wednesday 31st

- 8:30 am Morning tea / coffee
- 9:00 am Addressing challenges researchers face when visualising and interpreting proteomics data interactively
- 10:00 am Morning tea and networking
- 10:30 am Next steps for the Computational Proteomics Community: 2024 and beyond
- 11:00 am Meeting close & walk to bus stop for trip to Lorne
- 12:00 pm Bus leaves for Lorne

Australian **BioCommons**

Australia's 23 National Research Infrastructures

Australian Government

Physics

Telescopes

Microscopes

Environment

Human

Biology

Computational

Infrastructure supporting omics use in life science

Australian Government

National Research
Infrastructure for Australia

An Australian Government Initiative

BIOPLATFORMS
AUSTRALIA

Est. 2007

Mission: to provide access to 'omics technologies in support of all Australian life science researchers working across human health, agriculture, biodiversity and industry.

Infrastructure supporting omics use in life science

Australian Government

**BIOPLATFORMS
AUSTRALIA**

Est. 2007

Mission: to provide access to 'omics technologies in support of all Australian life science researchers working across human health, agriculture, biodiversity and industry.

**Australian
BioCommons**

Est. 2019

Mission: To actively support Australian life science research communities with bioinformatics and bioscience data infrastructures at a national scale.

We identify what life science research communities need

Identify

Research

Communicate

Document

Deploy

And then deploy services for anyone to use

Identify

Research

Communicate

Document

Deploy

Bioinformatics Tool Finder

Australian AlphaFold Service

Australian BioCommons Leadership Share (ABLES)

Galaxy Australia

Training Infrastructure Service

ToolFinder

Australian BioCommons

This page lists bioinformatics tools and software that are installed across several of the BioCommons infrastructure partner systems. Tool / software status on other infrastructure partners. Can't find the software you need? Click here to see other options for finding software. Click to find out how to request installation of software on ToolFinder listed infrastructures.

Please note:

- NCI (IFRS) below refers to the Australian BioCommons Tools and Workflows repository, located in project allocation IR9 at the National Computational Infrastructure (NCI).

Name	Homepage	Registry link	Topic(s)	Publications	Containers available? (BioContainers)	Galaxy Australia	NCI (Gadi)	NCI (IFRS)
3D-DNA	3D-DNA		Sequence assembly Mapping DNA	The cross-assembly of the DNA-seq...	3d-dna			
AbvSS	AbvSS		Sequence assembly	DOI:10.1101/189531, DOI:10.1101/214568, DOI:10.1101/214568, DOI:10.1101/214568, DOI:10.1101/214568	abvss	AbvSS-2.3 (ngley)	2.2.3	
bandage	bandage		Genomics Sequence assembly	DOI:10.1093/bioinformatics/btt383	bandage	2 tools		
bellmouth	bellmouth		Transcriptomics Sequence assembly RNA-Seq Workflows	The Bellmouth pipeline (bioRxiv:161100)	bellmouth	Filter and merge (ngley)		
Booie	Booie		Mapping Genomics Sequencing Sequence assembly	Ultrafast and memory-efficient alignment of short DNA sequences on the GPU. DOI:10.1093/bioinformatics/btt117	booie	Map with Booie for Illumina-1.2.3		
BUSCO	BUSCO		Sequence assembly Genomics Transcriptomics Sequence analysis	DOI:10.1093/bioinformatics/btt693, DOI:10.1093/bioinformatics/btt693, DOI:10.1093/bioinformatics/btt693, DOI:10.1093/bioinformatics/btt693	busco	Busco-5.5 (ngley)	5.2.1, 5.4.0	
Cactus	Cactus		Genomics Sequence analysis Phylogeny Sequence assembly Mapping Phylogenetics	Progressive Cactus is a multiple sequence aligner for whole-genome assembly. DOI:10.1101/2016.03.02.088493	cactus	2 tools		2.0.3
Canu	Canu		Genomics	Canu: scalable and accurate long-read assembly. DOI:10.1101/2016.03.02.088493	canu	Canu assembly-2.2 (ngley)	2.0, 2.0, 1.8, 2.1.1	

<https://www.uniprot.org/uniprot/kb/P02768/entry#structure>

PROTEOMICS LAB

Welcome to the Galaxy Australia Proteomics Lab. Get quick access to the tools, workflows and tutorials you need to get started with proteomics on Galaxy. What is this page?

This page is currently under development in consultation with the Australian Proteomics Bioinformatics community.

Proteomics tutorials for Galaxy | MS data file format converters | MS reference data on Galaxy

AlphaFold 2.0 on Galaxy Australia | 9000+ Tools & Datasets Ready to install | Additional storage Available on request

Data import

Tools | Help

Some example tools are listed here: you can also search for more in the full tool panel to the left.

Import data to Galaxy

File conversion and modification

Tools | Help

Some example tools are listed here: you can also search for more in the full tool panel to the left.

ascconvert | Thermo

Database searching

Tools | Help

Calendar | Stats | Request

TlaaS

Training Infrastructure as a Service (TlaaS) for the Galaxy training community. You provide...

Priority job queue to service your training event effectively. See our [Event Dashboard](#).

No maintenance or administration required.

And then deploy services for anyone to use

Identify

Research

Communicate

Document

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Bioinformatics Tool Finder

Australian AlphaFold Service

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Galaxy Australia

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Name	Homepage	Registry link	Topic(s)	Publications	Containers available? (BioContainers)	Galaxy Australia	NCI (EaaS)	NCI (IR9)
3D-DNA	3D-DNA		Sequence assembly Mapping DNA	The cross-assembly of the DNA...	3d-dna			
ABvSS	ABvSS		Sequence assembly	DOI:10.1101/085512	abvss	ABvSS-2.3 (galaxy)	2.3	
bandage	bandage		Genomics Sequence assembly	DOI:10.1101/214368	bandage	2 tools (C)		
bellmouth	bellmouth		Transcriptomics Sequence assembly RNA-Seq Workflows	The Bellmouth platform...	bellmouth	Filter and merge (galaxy)		
Boatle	Boatle		Mapping Genomics Sequencing Sequence assembly	Ultrafast and memory-efficient alignment of short DNA...	boatle	Map with Boatle for Illumina-1.2.3		
BUSCO	BUSCO		Sequence assembly Genomics Transcriptomics Sequence analysis	DOI:10.1101/060808	busco	busco-5.5 (galaxy)	5.1 5.4.5	
Cactus	Cactus		Genomics Sequence analysis Phylogeny Sequence assembly Mapping Phylogenetics	Progressive Cactus is a multiple genome aligner...	cactus	2 tools (C)	2.0.3	
Catu	Catu		Genomics	Catu: Scalable and accurate long-read assembly...	catu	Catu assembly-2.2 (galaxy)	2.0 1.8 2.1.1	

<https://www.uniprot.org/uniprot/kb/P02768/entry#structure>

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Calendar Stats Request

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Discovery

Analysis

Resourcing

Shared platform

Training

How does this work?

Identify

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facilitate interactions with computational providers to build a more fit-for-purpose, flexible and cohesive data analysis ecosystem

How does this work?

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How does this work?

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Proteomics Bioinformatics Infrastructure Roadmap for Australia

V4.0

20 December 2022

O. Johan R. Gustafsson and Jeffrey H. Christiansen

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7460249

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Gustafsson, O. J. R., & Christiansen, J. (2022).
Proteomics Bioinformatics Infrastructure
Roadmap for Australia (4.0). Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7460249>

How does this work?

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A **shared platform** for primary proteomics bioinformatics analyses

Interactive environments to enable secondary analyses, visualisation, and exploration

Systems to enable **submission and retrieval** of raw (primary) and derived (secondary) proteomics datasets

A proteomics-specific **training** program

Alignment, adoption and contribution to **global best-practice** efforts

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Shared platforms #1

Identify Research Communicate Document **Deploy**

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AlphaFold 2.0 on Galaxy Australia
[Apply now](#)

9000+ Tools & Datasets Ready to install
[Request now](#)

Additional storage Available on request
[Request now](#)

Open, web-based platform for accessible, reproducible and transparent computational research

Currently 93 proteomics tools (> 1700 total)

600 GB, and more on request, for Australian institutional users

Tailoring compute performance to real world data

Working to emphasise those elements of Galaxy that are most important to proteomics users

Shared platforms #2

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Scalable DIA-NN

File	Description	Last Commit
Deprecated_RoninAWS	Added step 5 resource example	3 months ago
Scripts	Small typo in checker scripts	2 months ago
README.md	Small fixes to README	2 months ago
dot_wine.tar.README.md	Message about TBA dot_wine	3 months ago
pwiz_image_setup.md	Moved pwiz setup to own readme	3 months ago

Scalable DIA-NN

Introduction

This workflow implements the CLI installation of [DIA-NN](#) in a highly scalable fashion. DIA-NN is a tool that performs data processing and analysis for data-independent acquisition (DIA) proteomics data and was developed by Demichev, Ralser and Lilley Labs ([Ralser et al. 2020](#)).

The Windows version of the DIA-NN tool is used, in order to negate the need to convert wiff files to mzML, which proved to have [deleterious impacts on the results](#). Wine PC emulator is used to run Windows DIA-NN on [NCI Gadi HPC](#), a Linux platform.

Native DIA-NN processes the input samples in series. This workflow has been created to run these steps in parallel, to massively speed up the analysis of large cohorts and avoid the need for processing in batches and downstream batch correction.

To tease apart the DIA-NN run command into discrete jobs, we followed the steps recommended by the primary developers of DIA-NN and [quantms](#), described in this [Github issue](#). Quantms is intended to be a scalable nextflow workflow of DIA-NN, but currently does not work on NCI Gadi or Pawsey Nimbus (suspect that it is due to MacOS vs Linux incompatibilities) and hence this workflow was re-created here. Further, our workflow takes wiff input where quantms requires the extra 1-2 hour step of converting wiff to mzML, plus the concomitant negative effect on output.

Portability

As at 2023-10-19, this workflow uses `nci-parallel` utility to parallelise processing across the NCI Gadi cluster. As such, it currently works only on NCI Gadi.

Users are free to adapt it for use on other platforms, for example by replacing the `nci-parallel` parallelisation method with Open-MPI or job arrays.

A future release will see the workflow written in Nextflow. This imminent release will be portable.

Shared platforms #3

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Seqera platform

The Australian BioCommons Organisation

Interactive environments

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Monash Proteomics & Metabolomics Platform

LFQ Analyst
Analyze and Visualize Label-Free Proteomics output from MaxQuant (Galaxy Version 1.2.5+galaxy0)

Tool Parameters

ProteinGroups.txt *
7: LFQ Analyst on data 2 and data 1: Rscript

Experimental Design Matrix *
7: LFQ Analyst on data 2 and data 1: Rscript

Additional Options

Email notification
 No
Send an email notification when the job completes.

Run Tool

Help

LFQ-Analyst
A tool for analysing label-free quantitative proteomics dataset
<https://bioinformatics.erc.monash.edu/apps/lfq-analyst/>

Motivation

- Automate downstream statistical analysis of Label free quantitative proteomics data (generated by MaxQuant)

Input

- MaxQuant proteinGroups.txt file
- An experiment design table (tab separated file) containing three columns ("label", "condition", "replicate")

Data pre-filtering criteria

- Remove potential contaminants
- Remove reverse sequences
- Remove proteins identified only by sites
- Remove proteins identified/quantified by a single Razor or unique peptide
- Remove observation with high proportion of missing values (intensity values must be present at least 2 out of three replicates)

Citations:

- Shah, A. D., Goode, R. J. A., Huang, C., Powell, D. R., & Schittenhelm, R. B. (2019). LFQ-Analyst: An Easy-To-Use Interactive Web Platform To Analyze and Visualize Label-Free Proteomics Data Preprocessed with MaxQuant. *Journal of Proteome Research*, 19(1), 204-211. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jproteome.9b00495> Visit Citation

License: MIT License

References:

- bio.tools: LFQ-Analyst (bio.tools) (OpenEBench)

LFQ-Analyst

Home

Analysis

Advanced Options

Adjusted p-value cutoff
0.05

Log2 fold change cutoff
1

Paired test

Imputation type

- Perseus-type
- bPCA
- knn
- QRILC
- MLE
- MinDet
- MinProb
- min
- zero

Type of FDR correction

- Benjamini Hochberg
- t-statistics-based

Include single peptide identifications

Number of clusters in heatmap
6

Example LFQ data

Example Experimental Design file

Demo

User Guide

Choose a dataset to save
Results Save

SIGNIFICANT PROTEINS
769 out of 2389
32.2% of proteins differentially expressed across all conditions
Download Report

LFQ Results Table

Show 10 entries Search:

Gene Name	Protein IDs	Benign_vs_Malignant_log2 fold change	Benign
1 A1BG	P04217	1.34	
2 A2M	P01023	1.35	
3 AAK1	Q2M2I8	-1.45	
4 ABAT	P80404	-2.07	
5 ABCC4	O15439	-2.14	
6 ABCF1	Q8NE71	-1.34	
7 ABHD10	Q9NUJ1	-1.61	
8 ABHD11	Q8NFV4	-3.28	
9 ABHD14B	Q96IU4	-1.85	
10 ACAA1	P09110	-1.95	

Showing 1 to 10 of 2,389 entries
Previous 1 2 3 4 5 ... 239 Next
Refresh Table

Volcano plot Heatmap Protein Plot

Result Plots

Comparison: Benign_vs_Malignant Font size: 4

Display names
 Adjusted p values

Select protein from LFQ Results Table to highlight on the plot OR drag the mouse on plot to show expression of proteins in Table

Benign_vs_Malignant

Save Highlighted Plot Clear Selection

Proteomics-specific training program

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WEBINAR: Getting started with proteomics

Padula, Matt¹

How do mass spectrometers work?

- Charged ions in gas phase (electrospray)
- Transmitted through quadrupoles.
- Select groups of ions for measurement or fragmentation and then measurement of fragments.
- Ion (peptide) mass and intensity is measured by:

Time of Flight

get selected or measured by the quadrupole. They can be collided in here to generate fragments,

Orbitrap

HCD Collision Cell C-Trap

Orbitrap Mass Analyzer

API Ion Source

Ion Source Quadrupole analyzer Collision cell Pusher MCP detector

MS1 (Quadrupole)

MS2 (TOF MS)

Reflectron

Time-of-flight (TOF) chamber

extractor

detector

number of ions

m/z

Getting started with proteomics

 Australian BioCommons
2.3K subscribers

 Subscribed

 15

 Share

 Clip

 Save

448 views 7 months ago Webinars

Proteomics aims to identify and quantify all the proteins and peptides within a sample. Mass-spectrometry is the most common tool for proteomics and the wide array of methods, techniques and specialised approaches available have made it a popular method for probing cells, tissue and organisms in response to various stimuli or diseases. ...more

Proteomics-specific training program

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The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL <https://usegalaxy.org.au/tiaas/>. The page title is "Galaxy Australia - Training Infrastructure as a Service". The main content features the "TlaaS" logo, which consists of a grid of human icons in grey and yellow. Below the logo is the URL <https://usegalaxy.org.au/tiaas/>. A paragraph states: "Galaxy Australia is proud to provide Training Infrastructure as a Service (TlaaS) for the Galaxy training community. You provide the training, we provide the infrastructure and cover all costs." Below this is a section titled "Why TlaaS?" with four icons and corresponding text: a heart icon for "All costs are covered by the Australian BioCommons for Australian users.", a clipboard icon for "Priority job queue to service your training event effectively. See our [Event Dashboard](#).", a crossed-hammer icon for "No maintenance or administration required.", and a document icon for "Official Galaxy Training materials are regularly tested and highly reliable."

Aims of the forum

- **Help inform** an ongoing national response that aims to resolve challenges in computational proteomics
- **Contribute** to expert-led strategic discussions
- **Hear** the perspectives of leaders in proteomics
- **Get hands on** with Galaxy Australia and Proteomics Lab
- **Discuss** best practice interactive tools for proteomics
- **Learn more about** the Australian BioCommons Proteomics Bioinformatics Community journey to date
- **An opportunity** to get involved in future work
- **Network** with other proteomics researchers and computational proteomics specialists

Acknowledgements

Lorne Proteomics organising committee

Australasian Proteomics Society

Australasian Core Facilities (ACF) group

Thanks!

You can email me at: johan@biocommons.org.au

Presentations

Presentations

Paula Burton

Co-Founder, CEO

Mass Dynamics

Prof Dr Stefan Tenzer

Professor for Immunoproteomics

University Medical Center of the
Johannes Gutenberg University Mainz

Prof Dr Mathias Wilhelm

Professorship Computational Mass
Spectrometry

Technical University of Munich

Past, Present, Future

Open Challenges in ML-based proteomics

Mathias Wilhelm

Computational Mass Spectrometry

Technical University of Munich

Connections in computational proteomics

30.01.2024

MW is co-founder and shareholder of

- both operating in the field of proteomics -
- with no operational role in either company.

Exponential increase in ML/DL models

What my group is working on

- **Models for peptide property predictions**

- Fragment ion intensity – Prosit
- Retention time
- CCS/IM/CV
- Precursor charge
- Proteotypicity, Detectability, Flyability
- ...

- **Models for drug response prediction**

- AUC cell viability
- EC50 cell viability

- **Foundational models in proteomics**

- Spectra
- (Protein) Expression

nature

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NEWS | 26 July 2022

Could machine learning fuel a reproducibility crisis in science?

'Data leakage' threatens the reliability of machine-learning use across disciplines, researchers warn.

[Elizabeth Gibney](#)

- Training data and/or (pre-) processing scripts not made publicly available
- We approached the authors because “scripts will be provided upon request”

Quote: “I only had limited R experience and was not happy with my scripts, so I deleted them”

- Not even the authors can reproduce their study!

Comment | [Published: 27 July 2021](#)

DOME: recommendations for supervised machine learning validation in biology

[Ian Walsh](#), [Dmytro Fishman](#), [Dario Garcia-Gasulla](#), [Tiina Titma](#), [Gianluca Pollastri](#), [ELIXIR Machine Learning Focus Group](#), [Jennifer Harrow](#)

[Nature Methods](#) **18**, 1122–1127 (2021) | [Cite this article](#)

Interpretation of the DOME Recommendations for Machine Learning in Proteomics and Metabolomics

Magnus Palmblad*, Sebastian Böcker, Sven Degroeve, Oliver Kohlbacher, Lukas Käll, William Stafford Noble, and Mathias Wilhelm

Be on the lookout for (BOLO)

- Inadequate data size & quality
- Inappropriate partitioning, dependence between train and test data
- Class imbalance
- No access to data

Consequences

- Data not representative of domain application
- Unreliable or biased performance evaluation
- Cannot check data credibility

Recommendation(s)

- Use independent optimization (training) and evaluation (testing) sets. This is especially important for meta algorithms, where independence of multiple training sets must be shown to be independent of the evaluation (testing) sets.
- **Release data, preferably using appropriate long-term repositories, and include exact splits.**
- Offer sufficient evidence of data size & distribution being representative of the domain.

PROSPECT - Labeled Dataset for ML in Proteomics

- Aims to connect ML/DL community with proteomics community
- 838 k unique unmodified peptides
- 61.7 M spectra
- 5.7 B annotated peaks
- 24 B peaks in total
- Based on ProteomeTools

Next extension will be covering PTMs

Be on the lookout for (BOLO)

- Overfitting, underfitting and illegal parameter tuning
- Imprecise parameters and protocols given

Consequences

- Reported performance is too optimistic or too pessimistic
- The model models noise or misses relevant relationships
- Results are not reproducible

Recommendation(s)

- Clarify that evaluation sets were not used for feature selection, preprocessing steps or parameter tuning.
- **Report indicators on training and testing data that can aid in assessing the possibility of under- or overfitting; for example, train vs. test error.**
- Release definitions of all algorithmic hyperparameters, regularization protocols, parameters and optimization protocol.
- **For neural networks, release definitions of training and learning curves.**
- Include explicit model validation techniques, such as N -fold cross-validation.

Overfitting in Prosit

- Prosit trained, tested and evaluated on three independent sets (no shared peptides, to avoid CE)
- We also tested separating e.g. missed cleavages etc – did not make a difference
- We use early stopping; learning rate decay or oscillating learning rates

Be on the lookout for (BOLO)

- Unclear if black box or interpretable model
- No access to resulting source code, trained models & data
- Execution time impractical

Consequences

- An interpretable model shows no explainable behavior
- Cannot cross compare methods & reproducibility, or check data credibility
- Model takes too much time to produce results

Recommendation(s)

- Describe the choice of black box or interpretable model. If interpretable, show examples of interpretable output.
- **Release documented source code + models + executable + user interface/webserver + software containers.**
- Report execution time averaged across many repeats. If computationally tough, compare to similar methods.

DLomix

Python framework for Deep Learning in Proteomics.

To reproduce and develop Prosit-like models.

Koina

Community driven endeavour to make AI models for life science research accessible

Oktoberfest

Python package for collision energy calibration, rescoring search results and generating spectral libraries

UIs

- Make ML/DL available to “end user”
- www.proteomicsdb.org/prosit
- www.proteomicsdb.org/use
- koina.proteomicsdb.org

Be on the lookout for (BOLO)

- Performance measures inadequate
- No comparisons to baselines or other methods
- Highly variable performance

Consequences

- Biased performance measures reported
- The method is falsely claimed as state-of-the-art
- Unpredictable performance in production

Recommendation(s)

- Compare with public methods & simple models (baselines).
- Adopt community-validated measures and benchmark datasets for evaluation.
- **Compare related methods and alternatives on the same dataset.**
- **Evaluate performance on a final independent held-out set.**
- Use confidence intervals/error intervals and statistical tests to estimate prediction robustness.

Checking for biases and evaluation against SOTA

- Prediction performance does not differ a lot between peptides part of ProteomeTools or not
- Performance is dependent on factors such as precursor charge, peptide length

- ❑ Machine and deep learning is able to learn and predict peptide properties accurately
- ❑ Accurate predictions of peptide properties can improve results of proteomic studies substantially
- ❑ Many tools of varying complexity available today 😊

- ❑ The hype of deep learning is hitting science, hard. New reproducibility crisis?
 - ❑ Irreproducible model generation (data + code)
 - ❑ Non-transparent evaluation
 - ❑ Lack of understanding/knowledge what is learned or how it actually works
 - ❑ Lack of understanding what deep learning can and cannot do
 - ❑ Limited/Controlled availability and resources to reproduce work even if everything is available
 - ❑ ...

Summary and Outlook

- We see gains resulting from computational methods equal (or better?) to advances in MS
- But,
 - the hype of deep learning may (or did already?) create a reproducibility crisis
 - we need more standards in wet- and dry-lab to be able to make full use of public data and trained models
 - we need to implement safe guards for users (confidence and out of distribution)

Thank you !

Wilhelmlab

Wassim Gabriel,
Ludwig Lautenbacher,
Omar Shouman,
Mario Picciani,
Mostafa Kalhor,
Armin Soleymaniniya,
Zixuan Xiao,
Ayla Schröder,
Joel Lapin,
+ many many students

Federal Ministry
of Education
and Research

European Research Council
Established by the European Commission

www.Proteometools.org | www.ProteomicsDB.org | www.ProteomicsDB.org/Prosit

Afternoon tea

Strategic discussion

Addressing the key challenges in computational proteomics

Dr Johan Gustafsson
Australian BioCommons
University of Melbourne

Dr Nikeisha Caruana
University of Melbourne

Dr Ben Crossett
University of Sydney

Reminder of the roadmap deliverables

1. A **shared platform** for primary proteomics bioinformatics analyses
2. **Interactive environments** to enable secondary analyses, visualisation, and exploration
3. Systems to enable **submission and retrieval** of raw (primary) and derived (secondary) proteomics datasets
4. A proteomics-specific **training program**
5. Alignment, adoption and contribution to **global best-practice efforts**

Break out groups

3x groups

Post-it notes
Please add these to the
sheets on your table

Vote up ideas with
a + symbol

Strategic discussion

Proteomics users

Bioinformaticians

Those who need bioinformatics, but are not bioinformaticians

Researchers who understand proteomics, and don't code

Other groups that don't understand proteomics, and may not code

Intricate / complex proteomics

Analysing and making sense of the data

Being clear about complexity in experimental design vs. the bioinformatics required

Understanding global best practices

Curated set of trustworthy packages / tools (endorsed)

Where is data kept?

Cross-institutional challenges to data access

Sharing data at the end of a project

Meeting journal requirements

Other ideas and observations

Report back to group

Interactive session:

Preview of a shared platform for computational proteomics (Galaxy Australia and Proteomics Lab)

Dr Johan Gustafsson
Australian BioCommons
University of Melbourne

Dr Anna Syme
Australian BioCommons
University of Melbourne

An introduction to

What is Galaxy?

Galaxy Australia is a hosted web-accessible platform that lets you conduct accessible, reproducible, and transparent computational biological research.

A user-friendly web interface to a complex mixture of computing resources

A launching site for analysis tool(s) with pre-determined and scalable resources keyed to a user's dataset size

A repository for the reference data required to support analysis

Keep track of your analyses with histories

A workflow creation and execution platform: easily compose workflows using drag and drop

A data and results sharing platform: share analysis histories and workflows with colleagues

A global project with many instances, and shared architecture (tools, reference data)

A place for hosting training events via Training Infrastructure as a Service

Supported by training materials on the Galaxy Training Network

or, more simply:

A webpage, for data analysis

Tools

search tools

Upload Data

FILE AND META TOOLS

Get Data

Send Data

Collection Operations

GENERAL TEXT TOOLS

Text Manipulation

Filter and Sort

Join, Subtract and Group

GENOMIC FILE MANIPULATION

FASTA/FASTQ

FASTQ Quality C

SAM/B

VC

Nano

Convert Formats

Lift-Over

COMMON GENOMICS TOOLS

tools

The Genome Lab has just launched! This corner of the Galaxy is dedic...

Home News People About Support Docs

Galaxy Australia Genome Lab: The new online workbench for easier data analysis

Access ready-made tools, workflows and tutorials for

Data preparation Genome annotation Genome assembly

genome.usegalaxy.org.au Click to switch to Genome Lab

Galaxy Australia is an open, web-based platform for accessible, reproducible and transparent computational research. Galaxy supports thousands of documented and maintained tools that are free to use. We facilitate on-demand training capacities and provision 600GB for Australian institutional (and 100GB for other) users.

AlphaFold 2.0 on Galaxy

9000+

Additional storage

History

search datasets

Chloroplast genome assembly

49.6 MB 13

8: Flye on data 2: consensus

7: NanoPlot on data 2: Log Transformed Histogram Read Length

6: NanoPlot on data 2: Histogram Read Length

5: NanoPlot on data 2: NanoStats post filtering

4: NanoPlot on data 2: NanoStats

3: NanoPlot on data 2: NanoStats

2: sweet-potato-chloroplast-nanopore-reduced.fastq

1: sweet-potato-chloroplast-illumina-reduced.fastq

files

How does it work?

- Tools
- search tools
- Inputs
- FILE AND META TOOLS
- Get Data
- Send Data
- Collection Operations
- GENERAL TEXT TOOLS
- Text Manipulation
- Filter and Sort
- Join, Subtract and Group
- GENOMIC FILE MANIPULATION
- FASTA/FASTQ
- FASTQ Quality Control
- SAM/BAM
- BED
- VCF/BCF
- Nanopore
- Convert Formats
- Lift-Over
- COMMON GENOMICS TOOLS
- Operate on Genomic Intervals
- MiModD
- Fetch Alignments/Sequences
- GENOMICS ANALYSIS
- Assembly
- Annotation

PacBio HiFi genome assembly using hifiasm v2.1

Name
PacBio HiFi genome assembly using hifi.

Version
1: Jun 2nd 2023, 13 steps

Annotation
Assembly, visualisation and quality control workflow for high fidelity reads built from circular consensus
These notes will be visible when this workflow is viewed.

License
GNU General Public License v3.0 or later

Creator
Gareth Price
Katherine Farquharson
Add a new creator - either a person or an organization.

Tags
fastq hifiasm HiFi genome_assembly
Add Tags

Apply tags to make it easy to search for and find items with the same tag.

DIA-NN ☆ ▾ Run Tool

is a software for DIA/SWATH data processing
(Galaxy Version 1.8.1+galaxy2)

Tool Parameters

Input files ^

Input file - optional

No mzml, dia, wiff, thermo.raw or brukertdf.d.tar

Specify a run to be analysed

Spectral library ^

Generate a spectral library

No
Instructs DIA-NN to generate a spectral library

Perform deep learning-based prediction of spectra, retention times and ion mobility values

No
Instructs DIA-NN to perform deep learning-based prediction of spectra, retention times and ion mobility values

Spectral library - optional

No csv, tsv, xls, txt, binary, speclib...

Specify a spectral library

Library headers - optional

Specifies column names in the spectral library to be used, in the order described in Spectral library formats [name 1],[name 2],.... Use '*' instead of the column name if DIA-NN already recognizes its name

Use the input library 'as is'

msconvert ☆ ▾ Run Tool

Convert and/or filter mass spectrometry files
(Galaxy Version 3.0.20287.2)

Tool Parameters

! Please provide a value for this option.
Input unrefined MS data * required

No mzml, mzxml, mz5, mgf, ms2,...

! You must agree to the vendor licenses to run msconvert.
Do you agree to the vendor licenses?

No
This tool uses proprietary vendor libraries; to run it you must agree to the vendor licenses. Read them at <http://www.proteowizard.org/licenses.html>

Output Type *

mz5

Data Processing Filters

Scan Inclusion/Exclusion Filters

General Options

Output Encoding Settings

Additional Options

Email notification

No
Send an email notification when the job completes.

Run Tool

Help

MaxQuant ☆ ▾ Run Tool

(Galaxy Version 2.0.3.0+galaxy0)

Tool Parameters

Input Options ^

choose the type of your input files *

thermo.raw

! Please provide a value for this option.
FASTA files * required

No fasta dataset available.

Specify one or more FASTA databases.

identifier parse rule - optional

>([^\s]*)

description parse rule - optional

>(.*)

Modify parse rules if needed.

Search Options ^

Specify an experimental design template (if needed). For detailed instructions see the help text.

- optional

No tabular dataset available.

minimum peptide length *

7

Peptides shorter than this value will not be reported nor be considered

Galaxy Australia deployment | 2024

Key

- Pulsar node
- ◆ Main node
- AARNet connection

Benefits of Galaxy Australia

Training
GTN / TlaaS

Sharing
Histories / workflows

Workflow reports
Complex reports can be generated

TPV & resourcing

Workflows

Tailoring compute performance to real world data
Ability to configure and scale compute behind tools

We are not in this alone

Welcome to Galaxy Proteomics

This European Galaxy branches off from the main usegalaxy.eu server and focuses on one specific domain: Proteomics.

Galaxy Proteomics is a multiple-'omics' data-analysis platform with particular emphasis on mass spectrometry-based proteomics. It is hosted by GalaxyEU and maintained by the [GalaxyP team](#) from the University of Minnesota, USA.

GalaxyP Resources:

- [About Us](#)
- [Publications](#)
- [Conference presentations](#)
- [Workshops](#)

Content

- [1. Tutorials](#)
- [2. Gateways](#)
- [3. Research Projects](#)
- [4. News and Events](#)
- [5. Contributors](#)

Example application

Galaxy and SARS CoV-2

<https://galaxyproject.org/projects/covid19/>

<https://www.biocommons.org.au/galaxy-covid-19>

Initial analysis of COVID-19 data using Galaxy, BioConda and public research infrastructure (XSEDE, de.NBI-cloud, ARDC cloud)

DOI [10.5281/zenodo.3685264](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3685264)

Powered by: [usegalaxy.org](#) [usegalaxy.eu](#) [usegalaxy.be](#) [usegalaxy.org.au](#) [usegalaxy.fr](#)

Dannon Baker, Marius van den Beek, Dave Bouvier, John Chilton, Nate Coraor, Frederik Coppens, Bert Driesbeke, Ignacio Eguinoa, Simon Gladman, Björn Grüning, Delphine Larivière, Gildas Le Corguillé, Andrew Lonie, Nicholas Keener, Sergei Kosakovsky Pond, Wolfgang Maier, Anton Nekrutenko, James Taylor, Steven Weaver

This repo serves as a companion to our study describing the analysis of early COVID-19 data:

No more business as usual: agile and effective responses to emerging pathogen threats require open data and open analytics. [usegalaxy.org](#), [usegalaxy.eu](#), [usegalaxy.org.au](#), [usegalaxy.be](#) and [hyphy.org](#) development teams, Anton Nekrutenko, Sergei L Kosakovsky Pond. *bioRxiv* 2020.02.21.959973; doi: <https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.02.21.959973>

correspondence

Check for updates

Ready-to-use public infrastructure for global SARS-CoV-2 monitoring

To the Editor — The COVID-19 pandemic is the first health crisis characterized by large amounts of genomic data¹. Computational infrastructure can be a bottleneck for data analysis, amplifying global inequalities in ability to track SARS-CoV-2 evolution. This is an issue even in developed countries,

structure requires increment, because these figured and merical clouds ed and many king payments to cal. In developing ting infrastructure n cannot afford omputation. Here, effort by the ls free worldwide structure, p sequencing data also providing an lbal pathogen d on raw

Fig. 1 | Analysis flow for calling SARS-CoV-2 variants using Galaxy, ONT, and Illumina technologies; VCF, variant call format; TSV, tab-separated values; PE, paired end; SE, single end. For more information, see <https://covid19.galaxyproject.org>.

Where can I learn more?

Visit the Australian BioCommons service page

<https://www.biocommons.org.au/galaxy-australia>

Webinar: Introduction to Galaxy Australia

<https://youtu.be/0IzmfEbWtUU>

Learn via tutorials at the Galaxy Training Network

<https://training.galaxyproject.org/>

Galaxy has lots of features but they can be hard to find

The screenshot displays the Galaxy Australia web interface. On the left, a 'Tools' sidebar lists various categories such as 'FILE AND META TOOLS', 'Get Data', 'Send Data', 'Action Operations', 'GENERAL TEXT TOOLS', 'Manipulation', 'Filter and Sort', 'Join, Subtract and Group', 'GENOMIC FILE MANIPULATION', 'FASTA/FASTQ', 'FASTQ Quality Control', 'SAM/BAM', and 'BED'. A search bar and 'Upload Data' button are also visible. The main content area features a 'Galaxy AUSTRALIA' logo and a banner for the 'Galaxy Community Conference' (GCC2023) held from 10-16 July 2023. Below the banner, a paragraph describes Galaxy Australia as an open, web-based platform for accessible, reproducible, and transparent computational research, supporting thousands of tools and providing on-demand training and storage (600GB for Australian institutional users, 100GB for others). On the right, a workflow view for 'argyrophylla' is shown, displaying a 2.31 GB dataset with two steps: '6 : ERR2040348:reverse' and '5 : ERR2040348:forward'. The top navigation bar includes 'Workflow', 'Visualize', 'Shared Data', 'Help', 'User', and a 'Using 44%' indicator.

there are some shared workflows but they may not be easy to find - keywords, tags - inconsistent

there are lots of tools! but the list is long

there are lots of tutorials, but it may not be obvious just from the "help" button

We can make better use of this space to display relevant resources

The screenshot displays the Galaxy Australia web interface. The top navigation bar includes 'Galaxy Australia', 'Workflow', 'Visualize', 'Shared Data', 'Help', 'User', and a 'Using 44%' indicator. The left sidebar lists various tool categories: 'Tools' (with a search bar and 'Upload Data' button), 'FILE AND META TOOLS' (Get Data, Send Data, Collection Operations), 'GENERAL TEXT TOOLS' (Text Manipulation, Filter and Sort, Join, Subtract and Group), and 'GENOMIC FILE MANIPULATION' (FASTA/FASTQ, FASTQ Quality Control, SAM/BAM, BED). The central content area features a pink-bordered announcement box with a light blue header: 'On Thursday June 22 we will be upgr...'. Below the header are navigation links: 'Home', 'News', 'People', 'About', 'Support', 'Docs'. The main heading is 'Galaxy AUSTRALIA'. A banner image for the 'Galaxy Community Conference' is shown, with the text 'Galaxy Australia invites you' and 'GALAXY COMMUNITY CONFERENCE'. The banner includes the URL 'galaxyproject.org/events/gcc2023-10-16 July 2023' and the hashtag '#UseGalaxy2023'. Below the banner, the text reads: 'Galaxy Australia is an **open, web-based** platform for accessible, reproducible and transparent computational research. Galaxy supports thousands of documented and maintained tools that are free to use. We facilitate on-demand training capacities and provision **600GB** for Australian institutional (and 100GB for other) users.' The right sidebar shows a 'History' section with a search bar for 'search datasets'. The current dataset is 'RNAseq from Acacia argyrophylla', with a size of '2.31 GB' and '2' locations. Below this, two dataset entries are listed: '6 : ERR2040348:reverse' and '5 : ERR2040348:forward', each with view, edit, and delete icons.

This space has been designed to be a Galaxy Lab

The screenshot shows the Galaxy Australia web interface. At the top, a pink bar contains the text "Lab URL". Below it is a dark navigation bar with the "Galaxy Australia" logo and menu items: "Workflow", "Visualize", "Shared Data", "Help", "User", and a "Using 44%" indicator. The main interface is divided into three panels. The left panel is a "Tools" sidebar with a search box, an "Upload Data" button, and a list of tool categories: "FILE AND META TOOLS", "GENERAL TEXT TOOLS", and "GENOMIC FILE MANIPULATION". The right panel is a "History" sidebar showing a search box and a list of datasets, including "RNAseq from Acacia argyrophylla" with details like "2.31 GB" and "2" locations. A central pink rounded rectangle overlay contains the following text: "Information", "Links", "Tools", "Workflows", and "Help".

We are *definitely* not in this alone

SARS-CoV-2 Data Analysis	covid19.usegalaxy.eu
Galaxy for Ecology	ecology.usegalaxy.eu
Erasmus MC Galaxy webserver	erasmusmc.usegalaxy.eu
GraphClust2 Galaxy server	graphclust.usegalaxy.eu
Galaxy HiCExplorer	hicexplorer.usegalaxy.eu
Galaxy Human Cell Atlas	humancellatlas.usegalaxy.eu
Imaging flavour of Galaxy	imaging.usegalaxy.eu
Indian Community	india.usegalaxy.eu
Materials Galaxy workbench	materials.usegalaxy.eu
Metabolomics	metabolomics.usegalaxy.eu
Galaxy for Microbiome (ASaiM)	metagenomics.usegalaxy.eu
Galaxy for Microbiome (ASaiM)	microbiome.usegalaxy.eu
microGalaxy community	microgalaxy.usegalaxy.eu
Galaxy Machine Learning workbench	ml.usegalaxy.eu
NanoGalaxy for ONT	nanopore.usegalaxy.eu
Galaxy for Plant Biology	plants.usegalaxy.eu

PROTEOMICS LAB

Welcome to the Galaxy Australia Proteomics Lab. Get quick access to the tools, workflows and tutorials you need to get started with proteomics on Galaxy.

[What is this page?](#)

This page is currently under development in consultation with the [Australian Proteomics Bioinformatics community](#).

Welcome and invitation to contribute

Proteomics tutorials for Galaxy

MS data file format converters

MS reference data on Galaxy

Access key proteomics resources

Alphafold 2.0 on Galaxy Australia

Apply now

9000+ Tools & Datasets Ready to install

Request now

Additional storage Available on request

Request now

Request more storage

Apply to access compute intensive tools

Request new tools

Quantitative proteomics

Tools Help

Some example tools are listed here: you can also search for more in the full tool panel to the left.

MaxQuant

FlashLFQ

Access relevant software

Post processing and visualisation

Tools Help

Some example tools are listed here: you can also search for more in the full tool panel to the left.

LFQ Analyst

MSstats

Chat with Johan about joining the Proteomics Lab effort!

In relation to the roadmap

1. A shared platform for primary proteomics bioinformatics analyses
2. Interactive environments to enable secondary analyses, visualisation, and exploration
3. Systems to enable submission and retrieval of raw (primary) and derived (secondary) proteomics datasets
4. A proteomics-specific training program
5. Alignment, adoption and contribution to global best-practice efforts

Thanks to the Galaxy Australia team!

Mok, Madeline Bassetti

Gareth Price

Catherine
Bromhead

Justin Lee

Nuwan
Goonasekera

Igor Makunin

Michael
Thang

Cameron
Hyde

Tom
Harrop

Anna
Syme

Exploration of Proteomics Lab

- 1 Register / log-in to Galaxy Australia <https://usegalaxy.org.au/login/start>
- 2 Visit this URL to join TlaaS <https://usegalaxy.org.au/join-training/forum-comp-proteomic>

Exploration of Proteomics Lab

- 1 Register / log-in to Galaxy Australia <https://usegalaxy.org.au/login/start>
- 2 Visit this URL to join TlaaS <https://usegalaxy.org.au/join-training/forum-comp-proteomic>

Explore

Start an analysis

Ask questions

Break out groups

3x groups

Post-it notes
Please add these to the
sheets on your table

Vote up ideas with
a + symbol

Break out group discussion

What does Proteomics Lab enable for your work / your research?

Is this still a good idea?

What is happening internationally that would be good to see in Galaxy Australia?

Tools, functionalities, something else?

What is missing?

Tools, workflows, reference data, resources (e.g. GPUs)

What can be improved?

Was anything confusing?

Other ideas and observations

Wrapping up day 1

Welcome, again!

Acknowledgement of Country

In recognition of the deep history and culture of this continent, I wish to acknowledge the traditional owners and custodians of the land upon which we meet; and pay respect to elders past and present.

Kaurna people (Adelaide)

Wurundjeri Woi-wurrung and Bunurong peoples (Melbourne)

Housekeeping

In an emergency

Toilets

Any and all questions can be
added to our event
[shared document online](#)

Afternoon tea
Morning tea

Forum agenda

Tuesday 30th

- 1:00 pm Welcome and introductions
- 1:20 pm Invited speaker presentations & ask me anything
- 2:35 pm Afternoon tea and networking
- 3:00 pm Strategic discussion: Addressing the key challenges in computational proteomics
- 4:00 pm Interactive session: Preview of a shared platform for computational proteomics (Proteomics Lab)
- 5:00 pm Wrapping up day 1
- 6:00 pm Dinner - at own expense

Wednesday 31st

- 8:30 am Morning tea / coffee
- 9:00 am Addressing challenges researchers face when visualising and interpreting proteomics data interactively
- 10:00 am Morning tea and networking
- 10:30 am Next steps for the Computational Proteomics Community: 2024 and beyond
- 11:00 am Meeting close & walk to bus stop for trip to Lorne
- 12:00 pm Bus leaves for Lorne

Interactive session:

Interactive tools for post-processing, visualisation and data integration

Dr Johan Gustafsson
Australian BioCommons
University of Melbourne

Dr Ralf Schittenhelm
Monash University

Dr Pouya Faridi
Monash University

A typical mass spectrometric experiment

A typical mass spectrometric experiment

What do we define as interactive tools?

- Tools for **post-processing of proteomics data** from tabular quantitative information
- Tools that focus on **visualisation**, on the ability to **explore the data** and on **drawing meaning**

Tabular
quantitative data

Like that created by MaxQuant, Fragpipe, others...

Interactive tool /
platform / system

A method by which a researcher can visualize, interrogate, explore, integrate and otherwise draw meaning from their data

Meaning derived
from data

A meaningful outcome could include new hypotheses, candidate proteins to validate, an answer to an experimental / biological question

What does currently exist?

OPEN / SANDBOX TOOLS

LINEAR / PIPELINED TOOLS

What does currently exist?

OPEN / SANDBOX TOOLS

LINEAR / PIPELINED TOOLS

Features
Workflows

Complexity
Required Knowledge

Flexibility

Ease of use
Ability to learn

Automation

Speed

What does currently exist?

ANALYST SUITE
LFQ-ANALYST

Features
Workflows

Complexity
Required Knowledge

Flexibility

Ease of use
Ability to learn

Automation

Speed

Summary Report

Interactive Results Plots

Enrichment Analysis

QC Plots

LFQ Results Table

Gene Name	Protein Cts	Benign vs. Malignant Log2 fold change	Benign vs. Malignant p_val
1	ALB	1.34	0.000815
2	AAM	1.09	0.0004
3	ANF	1.28	0.0002
4	MECA	1.22	0.00019
5	ABO2	1.28	0.00147
6	ABO2L	1.27	0.0012
7	ABO2L	1.27	0.0012
8	ABO2L	1.27	0.0012
9	ABO2L	1.27	0.0012
10	ACAA	1.24	0.0014

Upload Experimental Design Matrix

Browse... No file selected

Advanced Options

Start Analysis

OPEN / SANDBOX TOOLS

LINEAR / PIPELINED TOOLS

What does currently exist?

ANALYST SUITE
LFQ-ANALYST

Cytoscape

Proteus

OPEN / SANDBOX TOOLS

LINEAR / PIPELINED TOOLS

In relation to the roadmap

1. A shared platform for primary proteomics bioinformatics analyses
2. Interactive environments to enable secondary analyses, visualisation, and exploration
3. Systems to enable submission and retrieval of raw (primary) and derived (secondary) proteomics datasets
4. A proteomics-specific training program
5. Alignment, adoption and contribution to global best-practice efforts

Mini-interactive poll

<https://PollEv.com/surveys/BTWWiR1R8gRt1TtgS7Fxp/respond>

- BE INCLUSIVE!
- web-based vs download
 - free vs proprietary

Break out groups

3x groups

Post-it notes
Please add these to the
sheets on your table

Vote up ideas with
a + symbol

Break out group discussion

Which tool(s) are missing in the field

Where do you think the challenges are in making sense of proteomics data?

Access

Availability

Training / understanding the tools

Should you be required to program to work in proteomics?

Other ideas and observations

Morning tea

Next steps for the Australian BioCommons Proteomics Bioinformatics Community 2024 and beyond

Summary of this meeting

Invited speaker presentations

Strategic discussion outcomes

Onboarding and feedback for Proteomics Lab and Galaxy Australia

Discussion of interactive tools

Community

Summary of this meeting

Invited speaker presentations

Strategic discussion outcomes

Onboarding and feedback for Proteomics Lab and Galaxy Australia

Discussion of interactive tools

Community

Potential next steps

The community

The BioCommons coordinates a community for computational proteomics and bioinformatics, which aims to:

- **Engage** with Australian proteomics researchers, bioinformaticians and their collaborators
- **Provide a forum** for the community to share knowledge, connect and collaborate
- **Work with the community** to understand the bioinformatics challenges specific to computational proteomics
- **Identify gaps** in the community scale digital infrastructure available for proteomics
- **Co-create, align to, or adapt** best practice solutions that address these challenges and that can be maintained in collaboration with local and international infrastructures.

Proteomics bioinformatics community

Proteomics is the analysis of 'proteomes', which are the entire observable set of proteins in a given biological or natural system (e.g. tissue, fluid, environmental sample) under specific conditions and / or at a given time point.

FULLY SUBSIDISED RESOURCES AVAILABLE TO HELP AUSTRALIAN-BASED RESEARCHERS UNDERTAKE PROTEOMICS ANALYSIS

Australian BioCommons Tool Finder	WorkflowHub 	Galaxy AUSTRALIA PROTEOMICS LAB
Self-paced training materials Galaxy Training Network	Seqera Platform pilot service	Australian BioCommons training and events program

JOIN A CURRENT ACTIVITY

PROTEOMICS LAB Help us co-create content for [Proteomics Lab on Galaxy Australia](#).
If you are interested, please contact johan@biocommons.org.au.

JOIN THE CONVERSATION - ALL WELCOME!

The BioCommons coordinates a community for computational proteomics and bioinformatics, which aims to:

- **Engage** with Australian proteomics researchers, bioinformaticians and their collaborators
- **Provide a forum** for the community to share knowledge, connect and collaborate
- **Work with the community** to **understand the bioinformatics challenges** specific to computational proteomics
- **Identify gaps** in the community scale digital infrastructure available for proteomics
- **Co-create, align to, or adapt best practice solutions** that address these challenges and that can be maintained in collaboration with local and international infrastructures.

The community

- Meets once a quarter, where
 - Invited speakers present their work
 - Updates on in-flight activities are provided
 - Anyone can suggest topics
- We are looking to:
 - **Grow** the community
 - **Find** champions
 - **Continue identifying** infrastructure gaps, and pursue meaningful and feasible activities together with community

2023 Proteomics Bioinformatics community meetings

Speaker	Topic
Ori Livson ProCan / CMRI	Scaling DIA-NN and Cross Cohort Data Exploration
Nikeisha Caruana University of Melbourne	RDMassSpec Explorer: An online platform for the interrogation of rare disease proteomics data.
Rohan Lowe LaTrobe University	Introducing TlaaS – Training Infrastructure as a Service - for proteomics
Gareth Price Galaxy Australia	
Hailey Zhang Monash University	Phospho-Analyst: visualising and analysing phosphoproteomics data with "one-click"

Join the conversation

Join our quarterly meeting
and presentation series

Join our Google Group
discussion forum

☆ Proteomics Analysis 31 members

Welcome to the Australian BioCommons Proteomics Community Group

This group is for any Australian researcher (or their International collaborators) undertaking

- discuss proteomics analysis tools and pipelines with the group
- receive email updates or meeting invites on shared national infrastructure that is being developed
- influence how that infrastructure is developed so it is support their research

NOTE: To post messages to the group, you will need a google account (or link a non-Gmail account)

Feedback

<https://www.surveymonkey.com/r/forum-proteomics>

Acknowledgements

Lorne Proteomics organising committee

Australasian Proteomics Society

Australasian Core Facilities (ACF) group

Special thanks

Paula Burton

Prof Dr Stefan Tenzer

Prof Dr Mathias Wilhelm

Ben Crossett

Nikeisha Caruana

Anna Syme

Ralf Schittenhelm

Pouya Faridi

Pawel Sadowski

Christina Hall

Melissa Burke

Patrick Capon

Lorne Proteomics organising
committee

Australasian Proteomics
Society

Australasian Core Facilities
(ACF) group

Thank you!

See you in Lorne!